

Analytical Applications of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea. Part III. Gravimetric Determination of Nickel(II)

R. A. Nadkarni and B. C. Haldar

A new gravimetric method, based on the quantitative precipitation of nickel(II) as Ni(C₂H₅N₄S)₂ with amidinothiourea in hot alkaline solution, is proposed for the estimation of nickel. The error and standard deviation of the method are $\pm 0.3\%$ and $\pm 0.18\%$ respectively. Amongst anions, only cyanide interferes. The interference of cations, except Cu(II) and Hg(II), is removed by using suitable complexing agents. Separation of nickel from copper and mercury and its subsequent determination with amidinothiourea have been achieved. The present method has been employed to estimate nickel in alloy steel, stainless steel, and cupronickel alloy.

Dimethylglyoxime¹⁻² is a well-known and widely used analytical reagent for nickel. But nickel dimethylglyoximate is soluble in ethanolic solution containing not more than 50% ethanol by volume, in hot water (0.6 mg/100 ml), and in concentrated ammoniacal solutions of Co(II) salts. According to Vogel¹⁴ large amounts of Co(II), Zn(II) or Cu(II) retard precipitation of nickel dimethylglyoximate and Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(IV), Bi(III), Si(IV), and W(VI) should be absent. Difficulties arise when both Co(II) and Fe(III) are present because of the nickel complex being not pure. Other reagents³⁻¹² have been proposed for the estimation of nickel, but diverse ions interfere.

Amidinothiourea in alkaline medium furnishes with nickel an orange-coloured complex¹³ of composition Ni(C₂H₅N₄S)₂. In the present investigation, this reaction has been utilised for the gravimetric determination of nickel.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of analytical grade. The stock solution of NiSO₄ was prepared by dissolving NiSO₄·7H₂O (A.R.) in double distilled water and the strength of the solution was determined by estimating nickel as nickel dimethylglyoxime¹⁴. All other reagents were prepared as described earlier¹⁵.

1. Tschugaeff, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, **46**, 144; *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 2520.
2. Brunck, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1907, **20**, 834, 1844.
3. Atack, *Analyst*, 1913, **38**, 316, 448; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1914, **53**, 620.
4. Soule, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 981.
5. Rilley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 895.
6. Datta and Ahmed, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1961, **4**, 571.
7. Datta and Bhattacharya, *Science & Culture*, 1963, **29**, 155.
8. Belcher and Wilson, "New Methods in Analytical Chemistry", Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 1959.
9. Dave and Talati, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 735.
10. Dave and Patel, *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, **31**, 148.
11. Spacu and Dick, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, **71**, 442.
12. Fluck, *ibid.*, 1926, **69**, 232.
13. Ray and Choudhury, this *Journal*, 1950, **27**, 673.
14. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Pvt. Ltd., London, 1962.
15. Nadkarni and Haldar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 427; this *Journal*, 1964, **41**, 319, 813.

Procedure.—A 2% aqueous solution of 1-amidino-2-thiourea was added in excess with continuous stirring to a hot ammoniacal solution of nickel salt. NaOH was added, if necessary, to raise the pH of the solution above 10.5. Yellow precipitates appeared slowly. The solution was heated to boiling and the precipitates were filtered through a weighed sintered-bed (G_3 or G_4) crucible, washed with hot water, dried at 110-20°, and weighed as $Ni(C_2H_5N_4S)_2$. The conversion factor for nickel is 0.2004.

In some experiments, the results were checked by dissolving the dried and weighed nickel complex in dilute HCl and estimating the nickel as nickel dimethylglyoxime.

TABLE I

Estimation of nickel with amidinothiourea.

S. No.	pH.	Nickel.		%Error.
		Present.	Found.	
1	7.0	30.47 mg.	14.31 mg.	-53.30
2	8.0	..	30.45	-0.06
3	10.5	..	30.41	-0.18
4	11.0	28.67	28.61	-0.20
5	13.0	30.47	30.47	±0.0
6	..	30.80	30.85	+0.20
7	..	61.60	61.60	±0.0
8	..	55.44	55.52	+0.20
9	..	73.92	74.11	+0.25
10	..	80.08	80.13	+0.06
11	..	86.24	86.12	-0.14

TABLE II

Effect of cations on estimation of nickel.

S.No.	Cation present.	Complexing agent added.	pH.	Nickel.		%Error.
				Present.	Found.	
1	Fe(III)-195.5mg.	Na citrate	13.0	28.61 mg.	28.65 mg.	+0.20
2	Al(III)-161.9	..	..	..	28.59	-0.08
3	Cr(III)-104.1	..	..	..	28.65	+0.20
4	Ti(III)-465.9	..	10.5	..	..	..
5	Zr(IV)-228.1	..	13.0	..	28.59	-0.08
6	Th(IV)-696.3	..	..	..	28.56	-0.15
7	Ce(III)-350.4	..	..	..	28.59	-0.08
8	Sb(III)-549.4	Na tartrate	..	..	28.71	+0.30
9	Pd(II)-106.7	..	..	30.70	30.79	+0.30
10	Bi(III)-418.0	..	10.5	60.33	60.20	-0.21
11	UO ₂ (II)-1351.0	Na ₂ CO ₃	13.0	28.61	28.67	+0.20
12	Zn(II)-65.4	NH ₄ Cl	..	..	28.65	+0.20
13	Mn(II)-549.4	..	..	..	28.61	±0.0
14	Co(II)-469.5	NH ₄ CNS	10.5	60.33	60.50	+0.28
15	Sn(II)-296.8	NaOH	13.0	28.61	28.65	+0.20
16	VO(II)-254.7	H ₂ O ₂	..	30.70	30.75	+0.20
17	Cd(II)-449.6	KI	10.5	60.33	60.24	-0.15
18	Fe(III)-279.2	Na citrate	10.5	61.55	61.49	-0.09
	+ Co(III)-294.7	+ NH ₄ CNS				

TABLE III

Separation of Ni(II) from Cu(II) and Hg(II) and its subsequent estimation.

S. No.	Amount of Ni.		%Error.	Amount of other ions.		%Error.
	Present.	Found.		Present.	Found.	
				Cu(II).		
1	30.47 mg.	30.61 mg.	+0.45	158.6 mg.	158.1 mg.	-0.44
2	„	30.59	+0.40	317.7	315.6	-0.60
3	„	30.55	+0.25	635.4	633.1	-0.35
				Hg(II).		
4	34.24	34.19	-0.14	200.2	200.7	+0.20
5	68.48	68.32	-0.24	400.6	400.7	+0.01

TABLE IV

Estimation of nickel in standard alloys.

Alloy.	% Nickel.		Other constituents of the alloy (in%).
	In the certificate.	Found by ATU method*	
Stainless steel	8.20	8.14	Cr, 18.8; Fe, rest
Alloy steel	2.59	2.60	C, 0.34; Si, 0.25; S, 0.036; P, 0.014; Mn, 0.64; Cr, 0.75; Mo, 0.43; Fe, rest.
Cupronickel alloy	25.00	25.09	Mn and Zn in traces; Cu (present 74.50, found 74.54).

*Average of three determinations.

DISCUSSION

Results in Table I indicate that in the pH range 8-13, the precipitation of Ni(II) is quantitative. At pH 7 the precipitation is incomplete, whereas below pH 7, the precipitation does not take place. Nickel in the range of 28.67 to 86.24 mg. in 100 ml of the test solution can be determined by the present method with an accuracy better than $\pm 0.3\%$. The standard deviation of the method for 68.48 mg. nickel is ± 0.12 .

The following anions added in the form of their Na or K salts do not interfere in the pH range 10-13: sulphate, sulphite, thiosulphate, sulphocyanide, phosphate, pyrophosphate, halides, tungstate, molybdate, arsenate, vanadate, borate, carbonate, nitrate, nitrite, selenite, acetate, oxalate, citrate, tartrate. Disodium salt of EDTA prevents precipitation of nickel complex. So does the presence of cyanide. Nickel can, however, be estimated by decomposing the cyanide with H_2SO_4 (conc.).

The results of determination of nickel in presence of interfering cations are recorded in Table II. The interference of diverse cations, except Cu(II) and Hg(II), is overcome by using appropriate complexing agents. VO(II), when oxidised to vanadate with alkaline H_2O_2 , Au(III), and Pt(IV), do not interfere.

Separation of Nickel from Mercury and Copper.—Nickel is separated from Hg(II) by precipitating HgS with amidinothiourea in HCl solution of strength greater than 0.5N. HgS is filtered, washed with water, dried at 110°, and weighed as HgS. The filtrate is made alkaline to precipitate $Ni(C_2H_3N_4S)_2$ and nickel is estimated as described

above. With mixtures of nickel and copper, $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$ and CuS were precipitated with amidinothiourea in alkaline medium and then the nickel compound was dissolved in HCl . The precipitates of CuS were filtered and copper was estimated iodometrically. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$ was precipitated from the filtrate by raising the $p\text{H}$ above 10.5 and processed as reported earlier for the determination of nickel. As amidinothiourea does not produce the precipitate of CuS from acidic solution, it is necessary to precipitate CuS and $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$ first in ammoniacal solution and then to dissolve the nickel complex in HCl .

Determination of Nickel in Alloys.—The proposed method has been employed to estimate nickel in alloy steel and stainless steel samples of Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Yorks, England, and cupronickel alloy from Indian Mint, Bombay. Nickel was precipitated from the solutions of alloy steel and stainless steel in presence of citric acid and NH_4Cl and estimated as described above. In case of cupronickel alloy, nickel was first separated from copper and then estimated as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$ by following the procedure detailed under separation of nickel from copper. The results recorded in Table IV are in good agreement with the reported values for nickel.

It may be concluded that the accuracy of the present method is comparable to those of the standard methods for estimation of nickel as evident from the results of analysis of various alloys. In presence of suitable complexing agents, the interference by most cations is absent. Quantitative separation of nickel from copper and mercury and its subsequent determination are possible.

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, New Delhi, for the award of a research training scholarship to one of them (R.A.N.). Their thanks are also due to Dr. J. S. Dave of M. S. University of Baroda for supplying alloy-steel and stainless steel samples and to the Authorities of the Government of India Mint, Bombay, for supplying the cupronickel alloy.

INORGANIC AND NUCLEAR CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY-1.

Received August 22, 1964.